

THE PLACE AND ROLE OF A WOMAN IN THE MORAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE YOUNG GENERATION

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Abstract: in this article, the place, position, level of activity of the woman, who is considered the pillar of the family, in social life, her role in the acquisition and further enrichment of spiritual and historical values, the responsibility of the social, moral and labor education of the young generation, the incomparable position of women in the history of mankind, and the fact that the family is the main foundation of society is reflected. found

Key words: family institution, gender equality, repression, violence, social outlook, social mechanism, law, legal culture, socio-political activity, social protection, social stereotypes, family values.

The existence of the family is in itself linked to the priceless gift of children. The place, status, level of activity of a woman, who is considered the pillar of the family, in social life, her role in the assimilation and further enrichment of spiritual and historical values are important factors that determine the development of society. Another of the sacred duties of the family is manifested in the fact that it is a huge source of education. "The health of the family and the appropriateness of the relationship between parents and relatives creates a basis for the manifestation of common sense, positive virtues and intellectual qualities in the child" [1]

Abdulla Avloni, one of the progressive enlighteners, said, "Who does the education?" "Where is it done?" This is a mother's duty"[2], she answered. In fact, mothers are primarily responsible for the development of the nation. Another enlightener, Abdurauf Fitrat, said that "the mothers of the nation should receive education and knowledge, they should perfect their morals and knowledge" [3].

Jadids say that "without accepting women as full-fledged members of society, without correctly solving the family problem, without raising the young generation in the right way, it is impossible to reform the society, to direct its development towards development, in the end, the fate of the nation depends on the condition of its women and family [4]" - by determining the place of women in the family, increasing their status in society, ensuring equal rights in their participation in religious and secular affairs, enlightening them based on the fact

that women are the support of the nation, responsibility in the social, moral and labor education of the young generation, Since the cultural and spiritual level of any society is determined by the attitude towards women, they fought to implement such ideas as changing the negative attitude towards them[5]:

On the basis of these ideas of the Jadids, the incomparable position of women in the history of mankind and the fact that the family is the main foundation of society is reflected.

At the moment, the policy of caring for women carried out by our state, treating them with respect, in turn, is a certain responsibility for our women, i.e., to improve the social and spiritual environment of society today, when ideological attacks are on the rise, to make the growing young generation worthy of their ancestors, and national - to educate in the spirit of loyalty to spiritual values, to correctly interpret the essence of the holy religion of Islam, to protect young people from the influence of various harmful currents, to lean and rely on women in solving the most urgent issues related to the future of our country, to use their energy and intelligence wisely. he himself demands[6].

Values such as gratitude, contentment, tolerance, respect for elders, and loyalty to the place of birth, which are of primary importance in our lives until today, have been enriched and renewed over time.

Value is embedded in the thinking of people, consists of material and spiritual wealth of social importance, and arises in connection with a set of things and events that are beneficial for people's activities in various fields, first of all, production and labor. Natural and social phenomena become valuable as a result of the production of material and spiritual wealth, creative activity of a person, as a result of meeting his needs. Values belonging to the second category are one of the manifestations of human spiritual maturity, thanks to which society flourishes and citizens' dreams of happiness come true. Values are a certain system of highly formed moral qualities and virtues that are relatively stable, gain stability, express and manifest their identity in economic, political, legal, spiritual-cultural, daily household activities of every person, nation, nation, people, and are highly valued and respected. consists of National-spiritual values include humanity, community, justice, legality, patriotism, politeness and decency, simplicity and modesty, honesty and truthfulness, openness and bravery, generosity and benevolence, mutual respect, friendliness, sincerity, patience, imagination and purity. , patronage and generosity, dedication, loyalty, love, hard work, health, courage, etc.

Values are directly related to the culture, lifestyle, specific characteristics of work, beliefs, psychology, religious views, national interests, and ideology of different peoples. This causes values to acquire a national and regional image. Therefore, the approach to values, the criteria for their determination, and the level of adherence to them will not be exactly the same in different nations. This is how national aspects of values are formed. Each nation is not only a creator of its values, but also a preserver and transmitter of its values to future generations. Each nation is responsible for the preservation of national moral values. This responsibility means that the moral duty formed in the process of national development is not specific to individuals, but to the entire nation. Even in nations that lived under colonial conditions, national values do not disappear completely.

Female spirituality plays a key role in ensuring the stability of the spiritual and moral environment in the family. It is known that in the way of life of our people, the values that cover the customs, traditions and customs based on the standards of etiquette are of great importance. The development of moral qualities such as thoughtfulness and thoughtfulness, gratitude and satisfaction, loyalty, dignity, and honor in people and loyalty to it occurs in the neighborhood. Besides being a unique school of education and example, female spirituality is a pledge of a healthy social environment and a healthy lifestyle. In this case, justice and cultural-spiritual criteria become a priority feature of the lifestyle. A healthy lifestyle, social activity of young people is also determined by its strong protection.

The aid organized by our state also shows the priority of moral qualities such as generosity and compassion. Generosity means showing generosity to orphans, widows, disabled people, and foreigners, and it is a feature embedded in the spiritual world of our people. Also, the advice of our elderly women based on their own experience, their achievements are of incomparable importance in making young people broad-minded, strong-willed and brave, and in forming feelings of national pride, national pride, and confidence in the future.

So, the place and role of a woman in the moral development of the young generation is huge. Because the purest and purest feelings of a person, the first concepts and ideas of life are formed, first of all, in the family through mother's upbringing. In fact, a woman's work in the family is an important object of raising a mature generation. In every family, the happiness and well-being, wisdom and intelligence of a woman ultimately ensure the stability and prosperity of society. That is why Allama Rezauddin ibn Fakhriddin said: "A nation whose wives are well-educated will be well-educated, a nation whose wives are uneducated will be

uneducated, and a nation whose women will be diligent, enterprising, and willful will be rich." People will always be as women want, if you need great and virtuous people, teach women greatness and virtues[7]". Therefore, every woman should deeply understand the opportunities given to her as an honored representative of the social category in our society, and through her thinking and worldview, she should serve to stabilize the moral and moral environment of the society, justify the name of an honorable woman.

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